

A CASE STUDY OF AN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION STUDENT RAISED SOLELY BY GRANDPARENTS

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A Case Study of an Elementary Education Student Raised Solely by Grandparents

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Abstract

The main objective of this qualitative study was to gain a comprehensive Understanding of the experiences of elementary education student raised solely by grandparents since birth without parental presence. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating two elementary education student raised solely by grandparents and her/his best friend or cousin will serve as informant. All of them participated in the in-depth interview. Through thematic analysis, patterns and common themes that emerged From the participants' experiences were identified and grouped. This allowed for the extraction of core themes related to the challenges and strategies employed by elementary education student raised solely by grandparents. results revealed the unique characteristics of the participants: being unprioritized, needing financial support, having motivation, and feeling unsupported. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following challenges encountered: confronting financial struggles, navigating emotional struggles, enduring financial constraints and household, and feeling lack of support. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following coping strategies overcome the challenges: they arrived at the following ways of coping mechanisms: handling adversity with guidance, drawing strength from grandparents, preserving for generalization gratitude, and trusting god; they arrived at the following insights the advice and recommendation of the elementary education student raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth; seeking comfort and guidance from guidance, uplifting each other through adversity, and pressing forward amid familial challenges. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, grandparents, grandchildren, and researchers.

Keywords: *grandchildren raised by grandparents, thematic analysis case study, Philippines*

Introduction

Many students were raised by their grandparents, encountering various challenges and unique experiences in this familial setup. Some students have grandparents who have acted as their primary caregivers from birth or a very young age. This responsibility often presents new challenges for grandparents, as they navigate the complexities of raising another generation. Despite these obstacles, grandparents gain an irreplaceable opportunity to bond deeply with their grandchildren. They report developing a much stronger connection and often find themselves reminiscing about their own younger year (Smith & Segal, 2020).

As a matter of fact, in the international context, particularly in United States, Millions of grandparents raise grandchildren with no parent. Grandparents who are caregiving for their grandchildren are facing a common challenges, such as a physical and emotional stress, financial strain, and disruptions in social activities due to their caregiving responsibilities. There are numerous reasons why grandparents end up raising a family once more. Grandparents are their deteriorating health negatively affects their ability to provide care, thereby impacting their overall well-being and quality of life specially for their educational situation for their grandchildren need of support for financial needs of grandchildren (Maguire, 2022).

Meanwhile, in Cebu City, Philippines, grandparents who find themselves raising their grandchildren due to various family circumstances. While they take on this responsibility to ensure the well-being and upbringing of their grandchildren. They may sacrifice their own energy, finances, and personal well-being, as there is a lack of social benefits or support systems to aid them in their caregiving role. This situation not only affects their physical and financial health but also their emotional and psychological well-being. Despite their sacrifices, these grandparents often do not receive recognition or assistance from society, leaving them unsupported in their challenging caregiving responsibilities (Sadang & Uy, 2021).

This study is of paramount importance as it underscores the critical need for care and affection for grandchildren when their parents are absent. The research will provide significant benefits not only to the immediate family but also to all involved, by offering accurate and precise information on how to effectively support and nurture grandchildren raised solely by their grandparents. Given that grandparents bear the full-time responsibility of providing essential affection and guidance to these children, this study is an urgent necessity for further investigation. In times of hardship and adversity, supporting the family becomes a vital duty of grandparents. Moreover, grandchildren often seek guidance and inspiration from their grandparents, viewing them as role models in navigating life's challenges. Consequently, elementary education students raised by their grandparents have unique experiences that require immediate attention and examination. Addressing this issue promptly is therefore a priority.

In this context, several related studies have explored the experiences and challenges of grandchildren raised by grandparents. Notably, Xu et al. (2022) conducted a systematic review titled "Intervention to Improve Outcomes of Grandchildren Raised by Grandparents" which examined the effectiveness of various interventions aimed at improving the outcomes for these grandchildren. Similarly, Clark and Kelly (2022), in their study "Needs of Grandparents Raising Grandchildren" investigated the needs and challenges faced by

grandparents in this caregiving role. However, This study stands out by specifically examining the distinct experiences of elementary education students who were raised by their grandparents. This study will conducted in-depth interviews with these students to gain valuable insights into their specific challenges and experiences, offering a more nuanced understanding of their needs and circumstances.

Upon the completion of this study, dissemination efforts would be done to encourage the readers and members of the academy community to disseminate further and utilize the findings of this study. A free copy of the study would be given to school where this study would be conducted. Further, I would guarantee the publication this study in a reputable and refereed journal to encourage further the dissemination of this study.

Research Questions

This research aimed to find out the experiences of Elementary education student. Consequently, the key questions addressed included the following:

1. What are the unique characteristics of each case of Elementary education student raised by solely by grandparents?
2. What are the challenges of faced by of Elementary education student as solely being raised by grandparents?
3. What are the ways of coping mechanisms of each case of elementary education student raised solely by grandparents?
4. What are the insights of each case of Elementary education student raised solely by grandparents?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design with a case study approach. According to Rashid et al. (2019), qualitative case studies offer a detailed analysis of specific events in a certain context. Additionally, this design included a systematic method for gathering information about the phenomenon through interviews and interactive discussions, allowing for an understanding of experiences, viewpoints, insights, and particular observable situations.

This study employed a qualitative research design as its chosen methodology. This approach facilitated the collection of essential data to gain insight into the lived experiences of president's list achievers throughout their academic excellence journey. By conducting interviews to capture the unique characteristic, experiences, challenges, and insights of the participants, and subsequently analyzing the data, a qualitative design was employed to thoroughly explore and comprehend the distinctive cases, statements, and perspectives of the informants.

Furthermore, a case study involves a detailed investigation of a specific subject, which can be an individual, group, location, event, business, or phenomenon. Case studies are commonly used in sociology, academia, medicine, and business research. They are useful for analyzing, assessing, and understanding various aspects. Essentially, a case study refers to an in-depth and organized examination of a particular individual, group, community, or other entity. By examining the similarities and differences among the cases in the study, a deeper insight into the overall cases can be obtained (Heale & Twycross, 2017).

In this study, the chosen method is a case study approach, which served as a means to conduct an in-depth investigation into a specific issue within a historical framework. The researcher adopted this approach to examine multiple facets of the phenomenon, establish connections between various aspects, and gain a holistic understanding of the entire context, ultimately leading to well-supported conclusions. Additionally, the case study approach was well-suited for this study as it encompassed not only the participants' ideas that they desired to share with others but also their unique characteristics, experiences, challenges, and obstacles encountered during their pursuit of academic excellence.

Participants

The participants of this study were Elementary education students who raised solely by grandparents enrolled here at Kapalong college of Agriculture, science and technology. In selecting the respondents for this study, the purposive sampling method was employed to select participants in order to obtain genuine experiences for the study.

The criteria established by the researcher were suitable for the study. The participants were chosen according to specific criteria. The main individuals involved in this study were (1) Elementary education student who raised solely by grandparents and participant will come from BEED student here in Kapalong college of Agriculture, science and technology. The following were specified criteria for participant and informant in one (1) case:

Case 1: One Elementary education student who had been raised solely by grandparents since birth without any involvement from their parents. Only one best friend or cousin will serve as an informant for the participant in this study.

Procedure

As a researcher, I went through a series of processes to gather data and other essential information for the study. Before starting the study, I sought advice from my adviser to determine how and what steps would be necessary to complete it. In this way, even before

the study began, I had planned ahead of time.

I ensured that the data gathering processes are conducted accurately to facilitate a smooth analysis and interpretation process. I made sure to establish contact with the individuals I intended to interview and confirm their availability. Initially, I sought permission to conduct research with elementary education students who raised solely by grandparents were identified for this study. Since the participants were elementary education students from KCAST, I personally informed them about the research. It was important for me to clearly communicate the purpose and goals of my study to the participants.

Before the actual interviews, the participants had the opportunity to be informed about the purpose of the study. In this qualitative research, interviews were the primary methods employed for data collection. As described by Smith et al. (2013), these qualitative data gathering approaches aimed to provide valuable insights into the underlying processes and changes in individuals' perspectives. As the researcher, it was important for me to have a clear understanding of the research nature and purpose to introduce the participants and seek their consent to participate in the study.

Ensuring the trustworthiness of results is a crucial aspect of conducting high-quality qualitative research. One technique recommended for assessing the credibility of findings is member checking, also referred to as participant or respondent validation. Member checking involves the process of sharing collected data or research findings with participants to verify their accuracy and alignment with their own experiences. This technique is often listed as one of several validation approaches in qualitative research (Birt et al., 2016).

In collecting data, I took measures to ensure that the study's findings were ethically sound and trustworthy. My manuscript was sent to the research technical panel for a thorough evaluation. I wrote a permission letter addressed to the institution where I would conduct my study after securing the approval of all panel members. Then, I used the document to request authorization from the appropriate institution, specifically the Office of the President, to conduct the study.

Data Analysis

The collected data from the in-depth interviews were transcribed, translated, and analyzed following Creswell's (2009) proposed process for data analysis. The researcher followed the steps recommended by Creswell.

The responses of the participants, once translated, were systematically coded to facilitate a thematic analysis of the data within this single case study. Thematic analysis, often referred to as coding, encompasses the process of categorizing responses and identifying recurring themes in the text to construct a structured representation of thematic concepts. These discernible themes offer valuable insights within the data, which can be further subjected to analysis and measurement.

Through the systematic process of thematic analysis, the researcher organized the dataset into themes or patterns. This enabled the researcher to identify and develop themes based on the obtained data, as described by Naeem et al. (2021).

Throughout the data analysis phase, the researcher heavily depended on the transcripts and translated versions of the informants' responses. Employing a systematic coding process, the researcher categorized and structured the recurring responses to formulate an exhaustive thematic analysis. These concepts were methodically arranged and assessed, considering their interrelationships, commonalities, and distinctions, with the support of a data analyst.

Ethical Considerations

When collecting data from individuals, scientists and researchers adhered to ethical principles that guided their research designs and methods. The goals of human research often included understanding real-world events, exploring effective treatments, studying behaviors, and improving lives in various ways. It was essential to follow ethical guidelines during research to maintain scientific integrity, enhance the validity of findings, and safeguard the rights of participants (Bhandari, 2022).

Respect for persons was an ethical principle that emphasizes consideration for other people and acknowledges their inherent autonomy. By giving participants enough information about the nature and purpose of this research study in the participant's information leaflet in a comprehensible way to improve their informed consent, the concept of autonomy can be upheld (Kalu & Bwalya, 2017).

In this study, an informed consent form was created in advance for the participants. The form provided detailed information about the study, allowing interested individuals to learn more about it. During the interviews, the researcher respected the opinions and perspectives of the participants. It was crucial to establish a respectful relationship with the participants, considering their viewpoints, culture, and way of life, and giving them the choice to participate or not. The participants were always respected, as their importance was prioritized over the study. Before each interview, the researcher sought permission to record the entire conversation and the participants' responses. Additionally, the participants were made aware of their right to receive information about the study's outcomes.

Consent was formalized to safeguard individuals' right to decide whether or not to participate in the research and to encourage interactions in the research that are founded on respect "trust and integrity." It was crucial that a person's decision to participate in the research were voluntary and based on accurate knowledge about the implications of their involvement (Klykken, 2021). Ensuring the validity of consent was a fundamental requirement in the past.

In this study, the participants were encouraged to make informed choices and voluntarily participate, adhering to ethical research

standards. They were informed of their rights, including the right to ask questions during the interview, the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions, and the right to leave the interview without providing an explanation. If a participant chose to leave in the middle of the interview, the researcher respected their decision. The researcher assure that every participant is enthusiastic and motivated to contribute to the success of the study. During the interviews, the researcher obtained consent to record the entire conversation to capture a comprehensive understanding of their experiences.

Beneficence emphasized the importance of ensuring that participation was beneficial rather than risky. It required a commitment to minimizing risks for participants instead of prioritizing profit from their involvement. To protect participants, the identity of interviewees remained anonymous. Safeguards were implemented to ensure that participants were protected, with all information securely handled at all times (Bricki & Green, 2007).

The researcher secured a safe location for conducting face-to-face interviews, prioritizing the safety of all participants. During the interviews, participants were provided a secure environment where they could freely share their stories without fear of rejection or criticism. To mitigate psychological risks, the information gathered during the interviews was kept confidential and secure, minimizing the potential for negative outcomes such as shame or embarrassment.

Confidentiality the research prioritizes participant safety and confidentiality. Participants' identities were protected, and once the data was analyzed, all materials—such as videotapes, transcripts, and notes—were scheduled for destruction. Initially, some informants were hesitant to participate due to uncertainty about what to say. However, once I reassured them of the confidentiality of their responses, they became more comfortable answering the interview questions. I approached the questions with caution, treating the research with respect.

Each participant was assigned a unique code to ensure anonymity, following Republic Act 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. This law mandates that any information that could reveal participants' identities—like name, gender, ethnicity, or occupation—must be carefully managed. As a result, appropriate coding and safeguards were put in place. Additionally, participants were never required to provide their names on any forms related to the study. I also transcribed the interviews personally. The research data will be stored securely and destroyed three years after the study is completed. is concerned in the research and findings, as well as participant safety. The participants' identities were concealed. After the data has been evaluated, all items, including videotapes, encoded transcripts, notes, and others, should be destroyed. Some of the informants were apprehensive to be interviewed at first because they were unsure what to say, but once I assured them that their statements would be kept confidential, they gave me the opportunity to exhibit comfort in answering the interview questions. I am being extra cautious with the questions, and this research was treated with respect.

Justice relates to the idea that everyone who were involved in this study should be treated fairly. In my situation, I made sure that the participants were pick fairly using the correct method of participant selection, which was a purposive sampling method. It necessitates a fair distribution of risks and benefits as part of the research findings (Farrugia, 2019).

To ensure justice, the participants were not required spending any money as their contribution to the research was acknowledged. The researcher recognized the importance of all participants and credited them for their valuable contributions to the study. Their efforts were fully appreciated, and as a gesture of gratitude, practical tokens were provided to express appreciation for their involvement in the research.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of the study were elementary education students raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth and cousin/best friend serve as a informant. They all have their pseudonyms as they request to protect their identity. The participants were all kcast students. By that, the researcher put her trust on them that they could supply what this study sought to find out.

The interviews took place inside the campus, and the researcher spoke with them about where they preffered to be interviewed. The researcher got where she wanted to go, and both the interviewer and the interviewee were pleased with the end result, resulting in a seamless flow and open communication whenever extra or probing questions were required. Participants had the option of refusing to answer any question that they deemed unprofitable or against their choice. The data collected during the interviews was kept in strict discretion to guarantee confidentiality, and only the researcher and informant had access to any information that was expressed but not included due to the study's nature.

Table 1. *Participants of the study*

<i>Cases</i>	<i>Pseudynm</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Participant/ Informant</i>	<i>Code</i>
Case1- Elementary education students raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth	Ms. Red	Female	21	Participant	IDI-01
	Ms. White	Female	21	Informant	IDI-02

To adhere to the data collecting method, the researcher used her cellphone in place of the required tape recorder to record the replies of the participants. The researcher also asked all of the responders whether she may capture videos or photos during the interviews, but

they politely declined and instead requested that the researcher just record the whole conversation. All of them complied with the request, with the exception of one: that their identities be kept anonymous in the research (Boyce & Neale, 2006).

Categorization of Data

After the interview, recorded conversations were transcribed, translated, and subsequently analyzed. The researcher initiated the analysis through the process of coding. Coding was the technique of arranging resources into pieces of text before giving meaning to the information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the set of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation.

In order to classify the data, the major themes were given in order to address each research question. To give a detailed overview, the study's themes were thoroughly discussed and elaborated to provide a vivid description. Then came the conclusion and verification, which is the part of the investigation when the initial concepts and patterns regarding the findings are established (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

In order to add trustworthiness to the study, the researcher made note of the dimensions of credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. To address credibility, member verification was carried out in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to 1 participant so they may remark on it and certify to its authenticity. None of the informants had yet voiced any criticism of the transcript or offered any contradictory information. They all put their signatures on the participant verification form to indicate that they said yes. The triangulation of the study was made possible by the fact that it contained readings from participants and linked works, or more than two sources (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Creswell & Miller, 2000).

To ensure dependability and confirmability, the researcher provided an audit trail. This trail was established with the purpose of allowing the research review panel to validate the results, assumptions, and conjectures put forth in the study (Carcary, 2009). In terms of transferability, the researcher stated from the beginning that the results could not be generalized because these views were based only on the participants' own experiences in the indicated localities. Nonetheless, the researchers agreed that when the credibility, confirmability, and dependability of a qualitative case study are assured, then transferability is addressed as well (Klein & Myers, 2009).

Case 1- Elementary Education Student Raised Solely By Grandparents Without Parent Present Since Birth

This case was composed of Elementary education student raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth, and her best friend serve as a informant, their were enrolled in Kapalong College of Agriculture Science and Technology under the BEED program.

These participants were BEED students who raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth and her best friend serve as a informant. This study was focused on the challenges and experiences faced as a grandchildren raised solely by grandparents. She believed that even if your grandparents raised you, that is not the basis for believing that you will not be disappointed in your life and your studies, make them motivation in your life and always pray to god. She have a range of insights, including recommendation and advice to other, as they overcome the challenges as a grandchildren raised solely by grandparents without parent present.

Research Question No. 1: What are the unique characteristics of each case of elementary education student raised solely by grandparents?

This question was about the uniqueness of the participant include the characteristics, and experiences as a grandchildren raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth. In the responses both participant and informant there are four emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes are: being unprioritized, needing financial support, having motivation, and feeling unsupported.

Table 1. *Unique Characteristics of Elementary Education Student Raised Solely by Grandparents*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Being Unprioritized	<p>“The unique challenges experienced when I am with my grandmother are that when it comes to school meetings, I am not given priority by my grandmother to attend because she also has her own child who needs attention, so she needs to prioritize them.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“The unique challenges her experienced that I observed, .sometimes there were school meetings her grandmother did not attend.”-IDI-02</p>
Needing Financial Support	<p>“I was a member of the 4Ps program when I was in elementary school, so my grandmother helped me as I grew up, and my grandfather has a farm, and he works sidelines in our coconut farm.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“Based on my observation, before she became a member of the 4Ps program, that was the one to support her studying, and her grandfather had a farm to get their money to use to support her.” -IDI-02</p>
Having Motivation	<p>“From elementary until high school, I always received advice from my grandparents not to feel discouraged even though I no longer had parents to support my education.They always encouraged me.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“I think even she live by her grandparents, she continues to study, and she is not discouraged by the situation she was raised in by her grandparents.”-IDI-02</p>
Feeling Unsupported	<p>“Aside from not being able to join activities because there are activities similar to the candidates, when there’s a</p>

meeting, they need to attend those. And I cannot join because my grandmother does not want me to participate in those makeup-related activities.”-IDI-01

“The unique thing she experienced was her motivation from her grandparents to continue studying. Of course, sometimes she encountered struggles, but there was no reason why she stopped studying.”-IDI-02

Being Unprioritized

Being unprioritized is one of the unique characteristics that Ms. Red (pseudonym) experienced during school activities because her grandparents, who raised her, had other commitments that took precedence over school events. However, this was not a constant situation, as there were times when her grandparents could attend, demonstrating their effort to balance their responsibilities despite the challenges.

In the interview, it was revealed that the unique characteristics of the participant were being unprioritized. According to Ms. Red (pseudonym) the unique challenges related to her schooling . Her grandparents do not always prioritize attending school meeting because they also need to attend and resources her grandparents must manage, which affects their availability and support in aspects of her education : she Said:

“Mga unique challenges na experience nako nga naa ko sa akoang lola kay pag abot sa school na mga meeting diko ma priority sa akong lola ug tambong kay naa pud siyay anak pud nga kailangan pud niya unahon.” (IDI-01)

(The unique challenges I experienced when I am with my grandmother are that when it comes to school meetings, I am not given priority by my grandmother to attend because she also has her own child who needs attention, so she needs to prioritize them.)

Ms. White (pseudonym), based on her observations of the challenges faced by Ms. Red (pseudonym), noted the difficulties grandparents encounter in participating in school-related activities. She emphasized that the grandparents are often unable to attend school meetings or events, revealing a significant gap in the support system available to Ms. Red in navigating her educational environment: she said:

“Based sa akong nakita na mga unique challenges na experience niya kay usahay dili ma attend,nan sa iyahang lola kanang naay meeting or something nga magtagbo ba sa eskwelahan dili siya ma attendan sa iyahang lola.” IDI-02)

(The unique challenges her experienced that I observed, sometimes there were school meetings her grandmother did not attend)

Needing Financial Support

In terms of financial support, the participant highlighted the resources provided by her grandparents. Ms. Red (pseudonym) experiences vividly demonstrated the essential assistance she received from them throughout her upbringing. Her grandmother was instrumental, offering both emotional and practical guidance that significantly influenced her growth. At the same time, her grandfather’s efforts on their coconut farm not only ensured the family’s financial stability but also helped instill a strong work ethic in her.

In the interview, Ms. Red (pseudonym) shared that she became a member of the 4Ps program, which was designed to provide financial assistance to low-income families. She recounted how her grandparents played a pivotal role in her upbringing by consistently meeting her daily needs. They supported her not only with basic necessities but also through the resources generated from their farm. She stated:

“Elementary ko kay naapil ko sa 4ps mao nang na tabang tabangan ko sakong lola sapag buhi sakoa tapos akoang lolo pud kay naa man gihapon uma akong lolo gina sideline,nan pud niya ug mananggog pud gud bitaw niya halinon mana saamo.” (IDI-01)

(I was a member of the 4Ps program when I was in elementary school, so my grandmother helped me as I grew up, and my grandfather has a farm, and he works sidelines in our coconut farm.)

Based on the observation of Ms. White (pseudonym) that Ms. Red (pseudonym) has become a member of the 4Ps program, it was noted that her grandparents had also been farmers, ensuring their family's daily sustenance and providing crucial support to her: she said:

“Based sa akong nakita kay sauna apil.man sila sa 4ps then isa pud nang 4ps nga naka tabang sapag supporta sa iyang pag eskwela unya ang iyang lolo is naga kuan pud sa uma na makakuha sila ug kwarta mao to gamiton pud nila pag support.” (IDI-02)

(Based on my observation, before she became a member of the 4Ps program, that was the one to support her studying, and her grandfather had a farm to get their money to use to support her.)

Having Motivation

Continuing the exploration of the experiences of elementary students raised solely by their grandparents, Ms. Red (pseudonym) highlighted the vital role her grandparents played in offering personal and motivational support throughout her education. Despite her parents’ absence, their steadfast encouragement enabled her to remain resilient and determined.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) shared that until the personal and motivational support received from the Ms. Red (pseudonym) grandparents during their education. Despite the absence of their parents, she highlighted how their grandparents continuously encouraged them not to feel discouraged and to keep striving. This encouragement played a significant role in their ongoing determination and success,

underlining the impact of their grandparents’ emotional and motivational support.

“Sa una nag elementary hantud nag highschool ko kay always gina advice sa akong grandparents nga dili bitaw nako himuong discouraged bitaw ug wala nakay ginikanan diko mopadayon sakong pag eskwela niya sige jud ko nila gina tambagan ana mao tong hantud.” (IDI-01)

(From elementary until high school, I always received advice from my grandparents not to feel discouraged even though I no longer had parents to support my education. They always encouraged me.)

On the other hand, Ms. White (pseudonym) stated that Ms. Red (pseudonym) resilience and determination. She stated that despite living with her grandparents and facing different challenges, she remained undiscouraged by her circumstances. This highlights Ms. Red (pseudonym) perseverance and positive attitude towards her education and living situation.

“I think kanang saiyang lola siya nag puyo kay nag padayon lang gihapon siya ug eskwela bisan wala iyahang mama nipadayon lang gihapon siya ug eskwela bali wala siya na discouraged bisan paman saiyang naagian niya.” (IDI-02)

(I think even she live by her grandparents, she continues to study, and she is not discouraged by the situation she was raised in by her grandparents.)

Feeling Unsupported

As we go deeper into the stories, Ms. Red (pseudonym) conveyed feelings of being unsupported in her educational journey due to her grandparents’ limitations. Their inability to attend school meetings and participate in specific activities not only restricted her access to essential support but also left her feeling isolated. This situation may lead Ms. Red (pseudonym) to feel neglected or inadequate, as she might view her grandparents’ challenges as obstacles to her own opportunities.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) expressing limitations in her educational experienced due to her grandparents’ circumstances. She mentioned that her grandparents were unable to attend school meetings and that financial constraints prevent her grandmother from certain school activities: she said:

“Aside sa dili ko matambongan sa mga activities kay naa mga activities kapareha sa mga kandidata pag naa meeting gud kailangan sila.unya dili ko maka apil dili pud gusto si lola anang mga make up.” (IDI-01)

(Aside from not being able to join activities because there are activities similar to the candidates, when there’s a meeting, they need to attend those. And I cannot join because my grandmother does not want me to participate in those makeup-related activities.)

Ms. White (pseudonym) shared that the Ms. Red (pseudonym) motivation and resilience in continuing her education despite facing various struggles. She points out that these challenges do not deter Ms. Red (pseudonym) from pursuing her studies, emphasizing that her perseverance and unique experiences are key characteristics defining her academic journey.

“Ang unique experiences niya na gidala since nag college siya gihimo niyang motibasyon iyang lola ug lolo nga mag padayon ug eskwela sa college syempre mag lisud man jud pero wala na niya gihimong sukutan kay para e undang ang pag eskwela niya.” (IDI-02)

(The unique thing she experienced was her motivation from her grandparents to continue studying. Of course, sometimes she encountered struggles, but there was no reason why she stopped studying.)

Research Questions No. 2: What are the challenges faced by elementary education student raised solely by grandparents?

This question is about the experiences and challenges of elementary education student raised solely by grandparents since birth. What are those challenges faced as a grandchild raised solely by grandparents. In the responses of the participant, struggle and challenges her experienced while her growing up with her grandparents. In the responses both participant and informant there are four emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes are: confronting financial struggle, navigating emotional struggles, enduring financial constraints and household responsibilities, feeling lack of support.

Table 2. Challenges of Elementary Education Student Raised Solely by Grandparents

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statement</i>
Confronting Financial Struggles	<p>“The challenges I encountered while living with my grandparents were times when I wanted to buy something, but I felt embarrassed to ask them because they were the ones supporting my education that is why I felt hesitant to ask them.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“She encountered on finances. What I saw in her challenges since she was in college. Now we encounter struggles when it comes to obligations in our school. It is her challenges when she is with her grandparents.” -IDI-02</p>
Navigating Emotional Strugglers	<p>“I can see the difference in how other parents care for their children and how my grandmother takes care of me. There are times when I cry because why my grandmother raised me.I feel exhausted and stressed from school. I am embarrassed to share this with them.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“She and I are talking together, and she tells me about what she heard, what her grandmother said, or</p>

Enduring Financial Constraints and Household Responsibilities	<p>what her uncle said, why she is hurting, and she's embarrassed to talk with her grandparents." -IDI-02</p> <p>"The challenges that I have faced include times when I have experienced not having my own allowance, because my grandparents gave it to my uncle and aunt. That means I am not their priority and when it comes to doing household chores like washing dishes." -IDI-01</p> <p>"The challenges her experienced were her problems in her she said, I can do this. Or not? But she handled that because she has a dream in her life that if ever someday she repays a good for her grandparents." -IDI-02</p>
Feeling Lack of Support	<p>"The most difficult thing I have experienced is their support, because it is really important for a child to actually experience there is someone supporting them, the lack of support was the hardest thing I went through. Sometimes I did not feel supported." -IDI-01</p> <p>"The most difficult thing that she encountered was the emotional one that she had no one to be close to and also the school obligations, so she could say that I just stopped studying." -IDI-02</p>

Confronting Financial Struggles

Ms. Red's (pseudonym) journey embarked on an understandable journey that was marked by numerous challenges and adjustments. This confronting financial struggle exploration delved into the experiences shared by the elementary education student raised solely by grandparents, shedding light on the battles she faced when confronting the financial struggle of their challenges encountered. The challenges that she encountered provided valuable insights into the impact of being understood as a person or as a grandchild.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) shared her personal struggles with the financial dynamics of living with her grandparents. She described feeling embarrassed to ask her grandparents for additional purchases because they already supported her education and provided her basic needs. Despite her hesitation and embarrassment, she showed understanding of her grandparents' financial situation.

"Ang mga challenges nga na encountered nga naa ko sa akoang lola ug lolo naa'y time nga naa ko gusto paliton maulaw ko mangayo sa akong lola ug lolo kay syempre sila na ang naga supporta sa akoang pag eskwela mao nang maulaw ko mangayo bitaw sa ilaha." (IDI-01)

(The challenges I encountered while living with my grandparents were times when I wanted to buy something, but I felt embarrassed to ask them because they were the ones supporting my education that's why I felt hesitant to ask them.)

For the observation of Ms. White (pseudonym) the financial Educational challenges faced by Ms. Red (pseudonym) due to her grandparents' limited income sources. Her grandparents do not have employment outside of their current means of income, which presents difficulties in meeting school-related financial obligations.

"Mga challenges na iyang naagian kay financial jud na akong nakita na challenges jud saiya since karon nag college na siya na mag lisud jud me labi nag naay bayrunon sa eskwelahan mao na siya na mga challenges na naa siya saiyahang lola." (IDI-02)

(She encountered on finances. What I saw in her challenges since she was in college. Now we encounter struggles when it comes to obligations in our school. It is her challenges when she is with her grandparents.)

Navigating Emotional Struggles

Raising grandchildren can be both a profound responsibility and a source of immense emotional complexity. When grandparents become the primary caregivers, they faced unique challenges that can significantly affect their own well-being as well as that of their grandchildren. Understanding and addressing these emotional struggles are crucial for fostering a supportive and healthy family environment. Ms. Red (pseudonym) expressed her encounters with challenges that stemmed from their initial adjustment to the emotional struggles.

Experienced by Ms. Red (pseudonym) emotional experiences stemming from her unique family situation. It reflects her feelings of stress and embarrassment regarding the differences in parental care compared to her peers, as well as the pressure of academic life. She felt the need to continue striving hard in her studies to honor the tireless support she received from her grandparents, despite the emotional toll it takes on her.

"Makita bitaw nako sa uban pag atiman sa ginikanan ug atiman sa lola naa'y time nga mag hilak ko kay nganong sa lola ko nag dako naa jud times na feel nako kapoyon ko ma stress ko sa eskwelahan maulaw ko mag share sa ilaha bisan mo ingon ko na kapoy nako." (IDI-01)

(I can see the difference in how other parents care for their children and how my grandmother takes care of me. There are times when I cry because why my grandmother raised me. I feel exhausted and stressed from school. I am embarrassed to share this with them.)

Ms. White (pseudonym) shared the experienced of Ms. Red (pseudonym) she felt pain from comments made by her grandparents or uncle and she also felt a sense of exclusion or lesser value within the family dynamic, particularly in how her uncle treats her, emphasizing her status as a grandchild rather than a daughter.

"Mag estoryahanay man gud me ana niya then pag mosumbong siya sa akong nga naay mga nadunggan ug estorya saiyahang lola or saiyahang mga tito masakitan siya then maulaw pud siya moduol sa iyahang lola or lolo then ana siya maguol, siya masakitan, mahiubos

pud siya.” (IDI-02)

(She and I are talking together, and she tells me about what she heard, what her grandmother said, or what her uncle said, why she is hurting, and she’s embarrassed to talk with her grandparents.)

Enduring Financial Constraints and Household Responsibilities

The participant described persistent financial constraints and household responsibilities that influenced her experiences. She/he felt frustration over not receiving her own allowance, as her grandparents chose to support her uncle and aunt instead. This situation made her feel undervalued and neglected within her household. Furthermore, her participation in chores like washing dishes indicated that she carried considerable responsibilities, highlighting her sense of obligation and the lack of support for her own needs and priorities.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) stated the financial and personal challenges she faced. She mentioned that, in addition to not being able to attend school meetings, she does not receive a personal allowance because her uncle and aunt also have urgent financial needs. Despite these difficulties, her grandparents understand the situation and why she has to endure these hardships. Additionally, she contributes performing household chores.

“Mga challenges nga akoang naagian naa’y times nga ma experience nako nga wala bitaw ko’y balon kay nahatag sa akoang tito ug tita niya maong dili ko pud nila ma priority nila lola ug lolo ug mga trabahuon mang hugas ug plato.” (IDI-01)

(The challenges that I have faced include times when I have experienced not having my own allowance, because my grandparents gave it to my uncle and aunt. That means I am not their priority and when it comes to doing household chores like washing dishes.)

Moreover, Ms. White (pseudonym) shared that the resilience and aspirations of Ms. Red (pseudonym) faced significant challenges in her life as a grandchild, questioning her own ability to overcome these difficulties. Despite these doubts, she managed to handle her challenges effectively. She was motivated by a dream to repay her grandparents for their support and upbringing, demonstrating her gratitude and determination not to give up in the face of adversity.

Mga challenges nga naagian niya kay mga problema nga naabot saiyaha makaingon siya kaya paba nako ni? Or dili naba but gi handle niya na kay tungod naa siyay pangandoy sa kinabuhì nga inig abot sa panahon mobalos niya ang mga ikaayo saiyang lolo ug lola.” (IDI-02)

(The challenges her experienced were her problems, and she said, I can do this. Or not? But she handled that because she has a dream in her life that if ever someday she repays a good for her grandparents.)

Feeling Lack of Support

Recognition and understanding of the situation are crucial for effectively feeling a lack of support. The challenges shared by Ms. Red (pseudonym) shed light on the feeling a lack of support from grandparents can be challenging. It is common to desire a sense of connection, guidance, and encouragement from them, especially if you are navigating significant life changes or decisions. When grandparents are unable to provide the support you need, it might feel like you’re missing out on a valuable source of wisdom and emotional backing.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) shared that the most challenging aspect of being raised by her grandparents has been navigating their support, as it is crucial for a child to feel and experience that they have someone truly backing them. In terms of education, the lack of support was particularly difficult. At times, she did not feel adequately supported, which also had a significant impact on my emotions.

Ang pinaka lisud jud nga naagian nako kanang supporta kay mao man jud na’y importante bitaw isa ka bata nga ma experience nga naay nag support sa imoha ang support jud ang pinaka lisud naagian nako usahay dinako ma feel na supportaan ko.” (IDI-01)

(The most difficult thing I have experienced is their support, because it is really important for a child to actually experience there is someone supporting them, the lack of support was the hardest thing I went through. Sometimes I did not feel supported.)

According to Ms. White (pseudonym), Ms. Red (pseudonym) faced considerable challenges related to her school obligations. Overwhelmed by the pressure and uncertainty of how to address her situation, she felt had no viable solutions or support. Compounding her struggles, her grandparents lacked the financial resources necessary to provide the assistance she needed to continue her education

“Pinakalisud na again niya kay emotional wala siyay maduolan then isa mga bayrunon sa eskwelahan nga makaingon siya na moundang nalang ko kay wala nakoy maduolan or walay kwarta akong lolo or lola niya maka ingon siya moundang nalang siya.” (IDI-02)

(The most difficult thing that she encountered was the emotional one that she had no one to be close to and also the school obligations, so she could say that I just stopped studying.)

Research Questions No. 3. What are the ways of coping mechanisms of each case of elementary education student raised solely by grandparents?

This question focused on handling the struggles and coping mechanisms employed by elementary education student raised solely by

grandparents to address the Challenges encountered. The question aimed to uncover the various strategies on how to overcome these challenges. In the responses both participant and informant there are four emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes are: handling adversity with guidance, drawing strength from grandparents, persevering for generational gratitude, trusting god.

Table 3. *Ways of Coping Mechanisms of Elementary Education Student Raised Solely by Grandparents*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Handling Adversity with Guidance	<p>“The challenges that I handled when I was in elementary school were bullying. I would not have become like this if I had not allowed myself to become sensitive to these things and there were times when they could not attend to me because they also had priorities to attend to.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“Based on what I observed, when they talked, her grandmother gave her advice on what she should do if she had a problem, and that advice was appreciated by her grandmother.” -IDI-02</p>
Drawing Strength from Grandparents	<p>“They were my inspiration when I was growing up, since they raised me and provided for my daily needs. I saw their effort and cared for me properly.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“Maybe, the inspiration for her is her grandmother’s advice and the challenges she has experienced. Growing up with her grandmother as a good person and having dreams in her life, she never surrenders directly.” -IDI-02</p>
Persevering for Generational Gratitude	<p>“My motivation is my grandparents, and of course the most motivation in myself is to pursue studying i made them an inspiration in my studies until I finished because I wanted to repay their help when I was a child because they raised me since birth.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“Her main motivation is to handle the problem, don’t surrender immediately, and if she encounters a difficult situation, she will survive and work hard if someday she will become a professional, not based on what she has experienced.” -IDI-02</p>
Trusting God	<p>“First and foremost, the challenges I handled were trusting God. Aside from my grandparents, I told myself that God was my way of handling the challenges I have experienced. I told myself that without God, I wouldn’t be in the situation I am in now since God is my first comfort zone.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“For me, you will be a strong woman, do not give up on what you experienced, and always pray.” -IDI-02</p>

Handling Adversity with Guidance

Handling adversity with guidance is one of the ways of coping mechanisms. The voices of Ms. Red (pseudonym) handling the strugglers situation and the handling of adversity with guidance journey require openness, resilience, and a willingness to seek support from various sources. Support from family and guidance play a pivotal role in helping individuals overcome challenges and emerge stronger. By embracing guidance and leaning on the wisdom of others, individuals can navigate adversity with courage and resilience, ultimately growing and thriving despite life’s inevitable obstacles

Ms. Red (pseudonym) shared that during her elementary school, one of the most significant challenges she faced was bullying. It was a difficult experience that tested her resilience. Looking back, she realized that her response to this adversity played a crucial role in shaping who her today. Instead of letting herself succumb to the negativity, she made a conscious decision not to let it affect her deeply.

“Akong mga na handle na mga challenges sakong life katong elementary ko sa bully kung wala nako to na handle dili ko makaabot sa ing ani wala nako gihayaan himoong sensitive ko and naay mga times nga dili ko maadtuan tungod naay pud silay priority buhaton.” (IDI-01)

(The challenges that I handled when I was in elementary school were bullying. I would not have become like this if I had not allowed myself to become sensitive to these things and there were times when they could not attend to me because they also had priorities to attend to.)

Moreover, the observation of Ms. White (pseudonym) that during their conversation, the grandmother provided to Ms. Red (pseudonym) on how to handle problems she might encountered. She appreciated this advice, indicating a positive and nurturing relationship where guidance and wisdom are valued and welcomed. The role of the grandmother as a supportive figure in her life, offering counsel and reassurance.

“Basi saakong nakita lang kay in times na naga estorya gani sila sa iyahang lola murag gipahalagahan sa mga tambag kung unsay mga dapat na buhaton kung naa siyay problema”. (IDI-02)

(Based on what I observed, when they talked, her grandmother gave her advice on what she should do if she had a problem, and that advice was appreciated by her grandmother.)

Drawing Strength from Grandparent

Drawing strength from grandparents is a profound and enriching experience that can shape one’s understanding of Ms. Red (pseudonym), values, and outlook on her life. Her grandparents often served as pillars of wisdom, guidance, and unconditional love, providing a unique source of support and inspiration. Grandparents often embody resilience, having lived through various challenges and changes over their lifetimes. They offer a unique perspective on life, family, and values, rooted in traditions and personal history.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) shared that the significant influence her grandparents had during her upbringing. She acknowledged the care they provided throughout her childhood and emphasizes the crucial role their support played in her life. She also notes that her

grandparents are a source of inspiration for her, shaping her values and resilience through the experiences they shared together.

“Nahimo nako silang inspirasyon sa akoang pag dako since sila man ang nag buhi sakoa nag provide sa akong mga needs tapos naa pud mga times nga makit an nako ilang mga pag paningkamot hantud nga nag dako ko naatiman ko nila ug tarong.” (IDI-01)

(They were my inspiration when I was growing up, since they raised me and provided for my daily needs. I saw their effort and cared for me properly.)

Grandmother of Ms. Red (pseudonym) is her life and inspiration. Ms. White (pseudonym) stated that she draws inspiration from both the advice and the challenges she has faced while growing up under her grandmother’s guidance.

This upbringing not only shaped her as a good person but also instilled in her the determination to pursue her dreams and persevere through difficulties without surrendering.

“Siguro sa mga panambagon saiyahang lola no and then mga experiences na iyang naagian then gipadako pud siya saiyang lola na maayong tao then naay pangandoy sa kinabuhi then dili gane mo surrender dayon ing ana.” (IDI-02)

(Maybe, the inspiration for her is her grandmother’s advice and the challenges she has experienced. Growing up with her grandmother as a good person and having dreams in her life, she never surrenders directly.)

Persevering for Generational Gratitude

The persevering for generational gratitude, as illustrated in Ms. Red’s (pseudonym) story, highlighted the deep and enduring impact that family support especially from grandparents had on an individual’s drive and success.

The experiences of the elementary education student raised solely by her grandparents, underscored the significance of her motivation to excel academically. Her drive was not only a personal ambition but also a response to the profound gratitude she felt towards her grandparents, who had offered her unwavering belief and encouragement when others may not have.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) shared her motivation. Her motivation to excel academically stems directly from the profound gratitude she feel towards her grandparents. Unlike many others who may have been neglected or abandoned by their grandparents, she was fortunate to experience a different narrative. From the earliest days of her childhood. They believed in her when others might not have, and their belief became her driving force.

“Akoang motivation kay sila lolo ug lola syempre sila jud nang pinaka motivation nako nga mopadayon ko gina himo nako silang inspirasyon sa akong pag eskwela hantud makahuman ko kay gusto nako ibalos sailaha ang ilahang gitabang sa akoa gikan sapag kabata.” (IDI-01)

(My motivation is my grandparents, and of course the most motivation in myself is to pursue studying i made them an inspiration in my studies until I finished because I wanted to repay their help when I was a child because they raised me since birth.)

Trusting God

The voices of the participant during challenging times. Highlighted that trusting God served as a source of strength and comfort for an elementary education student raised solely by her grandparents, especially when she faced difficulties. Her experiences underscored the idea that faith acted as a foundation for resilience, providing both emotional support and guidance.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) shared her approach to overcoming life's challenges, emphasizing her reliance on faith. She believed that entrusting her difficulties to God is essential. She has convinced herself that turning to God is the most effective way to handle adversities, asserting that her current situation is a testament to God being her primary source of comfort and support.

“First and foremost jud akoang way nga mag handle sa mga challenges is trustIng god jud .aside sa akong grandparents gina saligan bitaw nako is ginoo jud naka ana jud ko kung wala ang ginoo kay wala ko sa akoang nahimotangan karon since siya jud isa sa kumbaga comfort zone.” (IDI-01)

(First and foremost, the challenges I handled were trusting God. Aside from my grandparents, I told myself that God was my way of handling the challenges I have experienced. I told myself that without God, I would not be in the situation I am in now since God is my first comfort zone.)

For Ms. White (pseudonym) to Ms. Red (pseudonym) encouraging her to see herself as a strong woman capable of overcoming her struggles. She advised to adapt her challenges, persist through difficulties, and maintain her faith and trust in God to help resolve any issues she faces. This advice is framed with the aim of bolstering her resilience and fortitude, emphasizing the importance of inner strength and spiritual faith in navigating life’s challenges: she said:

“Sakong paminaw kay be strong woman lang jud dili dayon mo surrender kung unsa may magian din mag ampo permi mga ing ana siya.” (IDI-02)

(For me, you will be a strong woman, do not give up on what you experienced, and always pray.)

Research Questions No. 4. What are the insights of each case of elementary education student raised solely by grandparents?

This question is about the insights of the elementary education student raised solely by grandparents, include the recommendation, and advices to other grandchildren raised solely by grandparents on how to overcome the challenges her/his encountered. In the responses both participant and informant there are four emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes are: seeking comfort and guidance from god, uplifting each other through adversity, pressing forward amid amilial challenges, nurturing bonds with grandparent

Table 4. *Insights of Elementary Education Student Raised solely by grandparents*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Seeking Comfort and Guidance from God	<p>“My recommendation is that you should always be open to God, and if there are people close to you whom you can share your problems with, you should talk to them about what you’re going through.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“Based on her experience, she recommends to others how to handle problems and to always be a strong woman. It is better to have someone to talk to when facing the challenges you encounter.” -IDI-02</p>
Uplifting Each Other Through Adversity	<p>Whatever challenges and difficulties they face, they should not let that discourage them from continuing their education, and let your grandparents be your motivation for that.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“Of course, they will use as motivation whoever raised them, and they will continue with their studies. If they have faced difficulties, they should use that as motivation not to surrender.” -DI-02</p>
Pressing Forward Amid Familial Challenges	<p>“If someone is in the same situation as me, just keep going. There will come a time when there are questions about why I ws raised by my grandma or grandpa. We should not let that be a discouragement in our lives that prevents us from pursuing our dreams.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“For me, you accept what you have in your situation now, you know how to be contented with what you have, and you do not compare yourself to others. You should not assume what you have now and be contented at all.” -IDI-02</p>
Nurturing Bonds with Grandparents	<p>“The advice I would give to continue their good relationship with our grandparents is to really listen to their advice, as there are no parents or grandparents who would advise us for our downfall. It’s also better if we open up to them.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“For me, you should maintain respect for them and love your grandparents to maintain your relationship. Of course, you should always show respect and be thankful to them.” -IDI-02</p>

Seeking Comfort and Guidance from God

Seeking comfort and guidance from God involves turning to a higher power for support, reassurance, and direction during her challenging times as Ms. Red (pseudonym), and she will recommend to others the same situation. Reassurance and direction during her challenging times. It’s a deeply personal solace through prayer and meditation. This process often provides a sense of peace, strength, and clarity, helping individuals navigate through life’s difficulties with faith and trust in a divine presence.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) offering her guidance, emphasized the importance of honesty with God, whom she regards as paramount in her life. She advocates placing trust in Him, believing that He provides comfort and support. She maintains that confiding in God is essential during challenging times, describing Him as her emotional anchor. She advises against internalizing problems, suggesting the presence of a trusted confidant to share one's burdens with.

“Ang ma recommend nako dapat jud always jud mag open ka sa ginoo kung naa mga tao nga naa sa imohang duol na pwede nimo ma openan sa imohang problema kay dapat naa jud kay ka estoryahan sa imong mga problema.” (IDI-01)

(My recommendation is that you should always be open to God, and if there are people close to you whom you can share your problems with, you should talk to them about what you are going through.)

Based on Ms. Red (pseudonym) experiences, Ms. White (pseudonym) shared her own, advocating that confronting challenges directly is essential for personal growth and future development. She emphasized the importance of seeking support from trusted individuals, underscoring that strength and openness are key traits in navigating life's challenges effectively .

“Basi sa experience niya na ma recommend sa uban pag handle sa problema then be strong woman as a always lang jud then mas okay man gud nang naa kay maka pagawsan in terms sa mga problema na imong maagian.” (IDI-02)

(Based on her experience, she recommends to others how to handle problems and to always be a strong woman. It is better to have someone to talk to when facing the challenges you encounter.)

Uplifting Each Other Through Adversity

The elementary education student raised solely by their grandparents, expressed the significance of support and motivation during difficult times. Uplifting each other through adversity involves recognizing that challenges can be overcome with perseverance and a strong support system. By encouraging one another, especially in the context of education, individuals can draw strength from shared experiences. Ms. Red (pseudonym) encouraged them to pursue their education regardless of the challenges they encountered, emphasizing that their grandparents’ support can serve as motivation in their lives.

The following were stated by Ms. Red (pseudonym) underscores the importance of not letting past challenges impede your educational journey. Rather, she urges you to harness motivation from your own determination and the profound inspiration passed down by your grandparents, who nurtured your aspirations. They have played a pivotal role in shaping your dreams. In the end, as the primary beneficiary of your perseverance: She said:

“Kung unsa ang mga challenges nga ilahang naagian mga kalisud nga ilang naagian dili to nila himoon ug discouragement nga dili sila mag padayon sa pag eskwela ug ang imohang mga grandparents maoy nag buhi sa imoha himoa na sila ug motivation.” (IDI-01)

(Whatever challenges and difficulties they face, they should not let that discourage them from continuing their education, and let your grandparents be your motivation for that.)

Ms. White (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of using personal challenges and difficulties as a source of motivation rather than surrendering to them. She encouraged resilience and perseverance in the pursuit of one's dreams, suggesting that obstacles should not halt progress but rather fuel one's ambitions and drive to succeed: She stated:

“Syempre himoon nilang motibasyon kung kinsa man ang nag padako sa ilaha up mopadayon sapag eskwela kung nakaagi man ug kalisud himoon na siyang motibasyon nga dili mo surrender.” (IDI-02)

(Of course, they will use as motivation whoever raised them, and they will continue with their studies. If they have faced difficulties, they should use that as motivation not to surrender.)

Pressing Forward Amid Familial Challenges

The experiences provided by the elementary education student raised solely by grandparents underscore the significance of Pressing forward amidst challenges to the act of continuing to move forward and pursue one's goals and aspirations despite facing difficulties within the family unit. This could involve various challenges such as conflicts, disagreements, financial strains, health issues.

If anyone has ever encountered a similar circumstance, Ms. Red (pseudonym) advised them to keep going because, in the event of a problem, it is common and the most crucial thing is to move on. We will not do that because of discouragement in our life to continue our studies and aspirations and make that incentive if ever that happens now. Instead, we should work harder to succeed.

“Kung naay same situation sa akoa padayon lang maabot jud sa time nga naay mga questions nganong sa lola or lolo ko nag dako dili nato na himoon ug discouragement sa atong kinabuhi nga dili ka makapadayon sa atoang mga pangandoy.” (IDI-01)

(If someone is in the same situation as me, just keep going. There will come a time when there are questions about why I was raised by my grandma or grandpa. We should not let that be a discouragement in our lives that prevents us from pursuing our dreams.)

Ms. White (pseudonym) advised against comparing oneself to others and suggests accepting one's current circumstances. However, she also encouraged not being complacent with one's current situation and not taking for granted what one currently possesses. This reflects an encouragement to continuously strive for improvement and growth while also being mindful and appreciative of the present.

“Para sakoa kay kabalo ka modawat kung unsay naa sa sitwasyon nimo karon kabalo sad ka makuntento gane kung unsa naa sa imoha ug dili ka dapat mag compare ug dapat sa imoha makuntento lang ka kung unsa naa sa imoha.” (IDI-02)

(For me, you accept what you have in your situation now, you know how to be contented with what you have, and you do not compare yourself to others. You should not assume what you have now and be contented at all.)

Nurturing Bonds with Grandparent

The elementary education student, raised solely by their grandparents, emphasized the importance of a nurturing relationship with them. Through personal experiences, the participant highlights the value of maintaining a strong bond with grandparents, stressing that open communication with them is crucial. Additionally, the student believed that neither parents nor grandparents can ever fully match the sacrifices made for their grandchildren.

Ms. Red (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of valuing and heeding the wisdom of grandparents in maintaining a strong relationship. It suggested that grandparents offer guidance based on their life experiences, and they genuinely want what is best for us. By listening to their advice, we can benefit from their insights and avoid potential mistakes.

“Akoang ma advice sailaha para ma continue ilahang good relationship sa atong grandparents is maminaw lang jud ta sa ilaha mga advice kay wala man jud parents or grandparents nga ma advice sa atoa para saatoang kapahamakan mo mas nindot pud jud nga nag open up jud ta sa ilaha.” (IDI-01)

(The advice I would give to continue their good relationship with our grandparents is to really listen to their advice, as there are no parents or grandparents who would advise us for our downfall. It's also better if we open up to them.)

As per the statement made by Ms. White (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of maintaining respect, love, and gratitude towards one's grandparents. It highlighted the crucial role of upholding these values in the relationship with grandparents, suggesting that these

elements are fundamental to fostering a positive and supportive family dynamic.

“Para sakoa kay e maintained na gina respito nimo sila permi then higugmaon nimo ang imong lola ug lolo para ma maintained ninyo ang relasyon then syempre sama sakong giingon ipakita jud nimo permi ang pag respito sa ilaha then magpasalamaton ka sa ilaha.” (IDI-02)

(For me, you should maintain respect for them and love your grandparents to maintain your relationship. Of course, you should always show respect and be thankful to them.)

Conclusions

The results of this case study provided an opportunity to explore and comprehend the real-life experiences, unique characteristics, challenges, coping strategies, and valuable insights of elementary education student raised solely by grandparents with this gathered information, this information underscores the necessity of recognizing their unique needs and the impact of their situations. The findings reveal that these students often face significant challenges In adjusting to their unique situations, which can impact their educational journey. To address these challenges effectively, it is essential to provide targeted resources and support. By equipping these students with the necessary guidance, we can help them navigate the transitions they face and better meet their educational needs.

Furthermore, elementary education students raised solely by their grandparents face challenges that, as shared by participants, include handling adversity with guidance, drawing strength from their grandparents, persevering for generational gratitude, and trusting in god. These strategies significantly contribute to their personal development. By overcoming these challenges, students can continuously grow and engage more effectively with their educational environment. Implementing these coping mechanisms equips them to handle struggles and access valuable support and guidance from their grandparents, ultimately fostering resilience and enhancing their overall educational experience.

Additionally, the findings underscore the significance of maintaining strong relationships between grandparents and grandchildren, highlighting their critical implications for family dynamics. Families need to prioritize these connections to enhance quality of life and improve relational outcomes. By recognizing the value of love, support, and mutual respect, families can foster positive relationships with grandparents. This commitment not only enriches these bonds but also promotes better life satisfaction and improved educational outcomes. Embracing the importance of continuous learning within these relationships is essential, encouraging growth and development as grandchildren navigate life with their grandparents.

Moreover, this research is vital for schools as it offers valuable insights into how to effectively support students raised by their grandparents. By understanding the unique characteristics and experiences of these students, educators can more accurately address their specific needs, ultimately enhancing their educational outcomes. Schools can implement targeted strategies to provide the necessary resources and guidance, ensuring these students receive the support they need to successfully navigate their educational journeys. This proactive approach not only fosters academic achievement but also promotes overall well-being.

Lastly, for future researchers interested in studying elementary education students raised solely by their grandparents, this case study offers valuable insights and a strong foundation for their own investigations. The findings, along with the review of related literature and the methodology used in this study, can serve as essential references for their research papers. This resource will not only aid in the gathering of necessary information but also inspire further exploration into this important area of study.

This case study included a sample of 1 participant and 1 informant who raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth. It is important to note that the selection of participant was restricted to this specific context, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other settings. Limiting the study to only 1 participant and 1 informant may restrict the generalizability of the findings and hinder the comprehensive understanding of elementary education student raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth experiences. The small sample size may not adequately represent the diversity and variability among grandchildren, potentially missing out on important insights and nuances. The findings may lack depth and statistical power, impacting the overall robustness of the study. It is crucial to consider these limitations when interpreting the findings and to recognize the need for larger sample sizes in future research to ensure a more comprehensive understanding of the case study.

This research used a case study approach where the researcher uncovered the essential structures and underlying themes that characterize the case under study. The researcher recommended that future studies may use a narrative research approach in conducting the study on elementary education student raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth because it will focus on understanding individuals' stories, experiences, and perspectives through the lens of storytelling. By capturing the personal narratives of elementary education student raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth this approach may allow for a rich exploration of their unique journeys, challenges, and growth as grandchildren. It may also provide an opportunity to uncover the contextual factors, emotions, and meaning-making processes that shape being raised by grandparents experiences. Narrative research provides a richer insight into the challenges and experiences of elementary education student as a grandchildren.

Lastly, a potential avenue for future research is to conduct a comprehensive Needs analysis to explore the specific needs and challenges faced elementary education student raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth this in-depth investigation could

identify experiences, and challenges of the participant

Additionally, studying the impact of tailored interventions based on the needs analysis could offer valuable insights for designing targeted personal development by gaining a deeper understanding of their experiences and addressing the needs, this research has the potential to better prepare and empower elementary education student raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth ultimately leading to improved the situation educational journey and educational outcomes while being raised by grandparents.

In pursuit of an undergraduate degree in Bachelor of Elementary Education-Generalist, the researcher conducted a study focusing on elementary education student raised solely by grandparents without parent present since birth. The research was met with approval from the panel members, assuring the researcher's commitment to approach it seriously. Despite encountering challenges, the researcher dedicated considerable time and effort to tasks such as interviews, data analysis, and presenting the results. Through perseverance, she/he overcame hurdles and completed the study successfully, aiming to leave a lasting impact on readers and establish the research as a credible and meaningful contribution to the academic community

Undertaking this research was a risk that the researcher willingly embraced, recognizing the potential for personal growth and dedication. The completion of this study not only fulfills the requirements for a bachelor's degree but also reflects the her/his unwavering commitment. Despite the obstacles encountered throughout the research process, her/his determination was tested but ultimately prevailed. This endeavor allowed for valuable experiences and lessons, highlighting the importance of perseverance and dedication in the pursuit of academic goals. She/he hopes that this study will make a lasting impression on its readers, being recognized as a noteworthy piece of work worthy of credibility and consideration within the field of education.

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